

Magnetostrictive behavior of NiFe₂O₄ synthesized by modified solution combustion method

Tulshidas C. Darvade, Bharat G. Baraskar, Pravin S. Kadhane, R. C. Kambale*

Department of Physics, Savitribai Phule Pune University, Pune, Maharashtra, India- 411007

*rckambale@gmail.com

Abstract

NiFe₂O₄ magnetic nanoparticles prepared at 600 °C by modified glycine/acrylic acid assisted solution combustion route; investigated its structural and magnetic properties. The phase formation and crystallographic information was analyzed by X-ray diffraction technique with Rietveld refinement. The microstructure reveals the formation of agglomerated particles due to non uniform temperature gradient during redox reaction, which is a typical characteristic of combustion synthesis. The magnetic parameters viz. saturation magnetization is 22.874 emu/g, retentivity 4.4325 emu/g, and coercivity 138.30 Oe is observed from magnetic hysteresis loop. Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy reveals the presence of octahedral and tetrahedral absorption bands which evidences the formation of spinel lattice. The magnetostrictive coefficient (λ_{11}) measured when magnetic field is applied parallel to sample and surface of the strain gauge; observed $\lambda_{11\max}$ NiFe₂O₄ is 11 ppm. The experimental design for studying the magnetostrictive properties of materials is discussed in this paper with case study of NiFe₂O₄.

Keywords: Ferrite, combustion synthesis, magnetostriction, spinel structure.